

A Review on the Strategic Planning of Tourism Enterprises in the Post-Epidemic Era

MengJie Huo^{1,2*}, ShuYu Li², JingXian Yan³, XiaoYi Zhang⁴, JinMing Wu⁵, Faieza Abdul Aziz⁶

¹Engineering Management, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

²Engineering Management, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

³Engineering Management, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

⁴Engineering Management, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

⁵Engineering Management, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400 UPM, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

⁶Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 43400, Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

*Corresponding author

Abstract:- The Covid-19 has been effectively controlled and epidemic prevention and control has entered normalization. However, in the post-epidemic era, many tourism enterprises still face many challenges in their development. Most of the current research focuses on the analysis of the impact of the epidemic on tourism industry, and less on the strategic planning of tourism enterprises in the post-epidemic era. This paper reviews the impact of the epidemic crisis on tourism enterprises and summarizes their response experience, so as to propose corresponding strategic planning and promote the high-quality development of tourism enterprises.

Keywords:- Covid-19, High-Quality Development, Post-Epidemic, Strategic Planning, Tourism Enterprises.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 is a major global public health emergency, and is the most widespread and far-reaching impact on China's tourism industry since 1979. As of April 20, 2023, the cumulative number of confirmed cases of Covid-19 reached 700 million worldwide, involving over 200 countries and regions, and the normalization of epidemic prevention and control will be the external environment for China's tourism industry for quite some time to come. Chinese tourism services were basically at a standstill during the

epidemic, and the World Tourism Cities Federation released its latest research findings, the World Tourism Economic Trends Report (2023). The report predicts that total global tourism revenues will recover to 86.2 percent of pre-epidemic 2019 levels in 2023, a recovery level 6.6 percentage points higher than in 2022. China's lifting of outbreak-related travel restrictions in December 2022 could significantly boost the recovery of tourism. Tourism businesses are gradually recovering in the post-epidemic era, but still face long-term tests. Lu Yang and Xia Jiechang (2020) noted that "Therefore, reviewing the impact of the epidemic on Chinese tourism enterprises provides strategic planning and development paths for the recovery and revitalization of tourism enterprises in the post-epidemic era."

II. LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE STRATEGIC PLANNING OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES IN THE POST-EPIDEMIC ERA

Chinese literature was classified through journals in CNKI for "advanced search". This article selected a time span from 2019 to April 2023, with the search term "tourism enterprises, post pandemic period, strategy planning". A total of 59 relevant literature were searched from the main database (Figure 1).

Fig 1 Distribution map of the number of Chinese tourism enterprises strategic planning documents in the post-epidemic era over the years.

From the figure, it can be seen that due to the outbreak of COVID-19 in 2020, China's research on strategic planning and management of tourism enterprises began in 2020. In 2021, the "post epidemic era" was proposed and the epidemic control in China was good, resulting in the highest number of literature. Afterwards, it gradually decreased year by year until China lifted its tourism restrictions in 2023, and the tourism industry began to gradually get back on track.

The research on the relationship between tourism and the epidemic at home and abroad is mostly cyclical after the outbreak of the epidemic, and such research gradually decreases. At the same time, scholars have relatively little research on the performance and experience of tourism enterprises in epidemic strategic management, lacking vertical time comparison and neglecting the planning role of the tourism industry. Only by conducting empirical analysis of the performance and practices of tourism enterprises and gathering various forces can the development of the tourism industry gradually improve in the post pandemic era.

III. RESEARCH CONTENTS OF THE STRATEGIC PLANNING OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES IN THE POST-EPIDEMIC ERA

Strategic planning is the art of creating specific business strategies, implementing them, and evaluating the results of executing the plan, in regard to a company's overall long-term goals or desires. It is a concept that focuses on integrating various departments (such as accounting and finance, marketing, and human resources) within a company to accomplish its strategic goals. The term strategic planning is essentially synonymous with strategic management. After the COVID-19 incident in the 21st century, the strategic planning in the tourism industry has gradually become the

focus of research scholars(Lu Hanlin,2020).

➤ *Research On The Impact Of The COVID-19 On The Strategic Planning Of Tourism Enterprises*

Enterprises face operating capital difficulties and brain drain. In the early stage of the epidemic, in order to quickly and effectively contain the spread of the epidemic, various countries and regions generally adopt strict border control measures, and the movement of people in foreign-related tourism may cause the spread of the epidemic across borders, so the recovery period of foreign-related tourism is at the very end of all tourism industry formats. Strict epidemic prevention and control measures have caused restrictions on the movement of people, difficulties in capital turnover of tourism enterprises, delays in repayment from upstream and downstream partners, increased bad debts of enterprises, and financial risks for tourism enterprises in the short term(Li et al.,2020).The persistence of the epidemic and the industry downturn have brought some mergers and acquisitions opportunities, but investors' concerns about the investment risks of the tourism service trade enterprises that have been suspended have increased and investors' investment confidence has been undermined. Even though the epidemic is basically under control, investors' enthusiasm for investment in the tourism industry will continue to decline, and the intensity and scope of investment will become more cautious. The continued conservative and wait-and-see attitude of investors makes it more difficult for enterprises to raise capital, further exacerbating the pressure on their survival. (Lin Mengjie,2021)

At the same time, the epidemic continues to hit the confidence and expectations of the employees of tourism enterprises, and the employment environment and salary of the employees are not guaranteed, and there is a large number

of departures and talent loss such as changing jobs, and even layoffs due to business difficulties, making the human resources pressure on tourism service enterprises in terms of business operation and business expansion even more enormous. So affected by the epidemic, at the business operation level, tourism service trade enterprises face the challenge of financial difficulties and brain drain in parallel.

IV. SUGGESTIONS ON STRATEGIC PLANNING FOR TOURISM ENTERPRISES IN THE POST-EPIDEMIC ERA

➤ *The Government Should Form A Strong Alliance With Tourism Enterprises*

In order for the tourism industry to recover, the government needs to issue directives to bring the various administrative departments together and integrate online and offline resources, which means that tourism companies need to remain open and actively work in concert with local tourism bureau, which can be reflected in the Chinese literature, Effectively coordinate the cooperation and mutual assistance among tourism enterprises, cultural tourism associations and tourism carriers, and further encourage scientific research institutes to provide suggestions for the revitalization of tourism. In order to maximize the performance of tourism enterprises, tourism companies must not only integrate their internal supply chains, but also integrate local cultural characteristics and local In order to maximize the performance of tourism companies, tourism companies should not only integrate their internal supply chains, but also integrate the supply chains of local hotels, scenic spots, and tourism distributors to create a full range of tourism services for tourists, e.g., (HaiShui Jin and Jinglin Xu,2022).online travel software can combine airlines, local hotels, resorts, outdoor camping, etc.For example, Ctrip can use its online traffic resources to cooperate with local tourism bureaus. In 2021, Ctrip cooperated and integrated marketing with tourism destinations such as Jiangsu, Henan, and Hainan, and had significant growth in tourism visits and revenue. Secondly, the governments of several destinations such as Heilongjiang and Hunan joined Ctrip in issuing subsidies for cultural tourism spending, an initiative that led to a 50% increase in tourism transactions.

➤ *Promote Integrated Development Of Culture And Tourism*

After the end of the epidemic, China's economy is on the rise, and people have good expectations. Especially after the epidemic, they have experience in epidemic prevention in behavior and have confidence in the future industrial development psychologically. Therefore, the tourism market has entered the fierce competition. In this situation, only by proactively breaking through the traditional mode, innovating tourism supply, constantly cultivating new business forms and opening up new channels can we release the vitality of tourism and usher in new development. Saying Zhu. (2020) proposes to promote the integration of cultural tourism. Due to the difficulty and high cost of shaping the tourism environment, prominent themes and distinct cultural characteristics become the key factors of product attraction, accelerate the flow of cultural and creative products plus tourism elements, encourage various resources to support related tourism enterprises, and promote the development momentum of "cultural tourism plus". In order to promote the integrated development of cultural tourism, it is necessary to respond to people's diverse needs, personalized cultural interests and cultural characteristics, gather people through different cultural functions and facilities, and retain people through culture. Not only to protect its external identity, but also to be more active and diverse. For example, the new connotation can awaken the old scene, the new collection of cultural memory symbols, to provide quality space for the new life, so that they can "sit down, stop, calm down", "sit down" is willing to spend time here, "stop" is to have a lot of consumption here, "calm down" is to have a clear impression of the memory of this place. Therefore, the careful excavation of local culture can better meet the diversified needs of the public, which is a good example of promoting local culture, and can help local culture go out. We will enhance experiential consumption, deepen the "destination - tourist" dialogue system, and enhance the two-way interaction between tourist destinations and tourists. In the post-pandemic era, the shift from outdoor to indoor small and focused family activities has great advantages (Jiani Jin et al. Inheriting and innovating local culture is a powerful force to promote the development of "cultural tourism +". Local culture reflects the spiritual style of a city and local people. Indoor activities of local culture with local characteristics are taken as innovation points to make cultural relics in museums and stories in ancient books come alive and go out, stimulate

the people's cultural confidence, and promote local culture with cultural and creative products related to cultural background. As well as the study of various cultural and creative products and cultural activities, so that local culture can constantly radiate new vitality. In the post-COVID-19 era, we are still faced with numerous challenges. A high degree of cultural confidence can forge the perseverance and courage to work hard. Only by continuously promoting the great development and prosperity of local culture and constantly enriching people's spiritual world can we provide a steady flow of spiritual motivation and empower the future development of cities.

➤ *Combine Tourism With Digital Media Technology*

The tourism industry is in crisis under the normalization of epidemic prevention and control, but on the other hand, there is crisis and there is opportunity, and tourism enterprises should seize the opportunity to achieve the phenomenon of recovery of tourism by combining tourism with modern digital technology, as mentioned in the literature digital technology enables high-quality development of tourism enterprises, and improving the governance model of tourism value chain is an important measure for the recovery of tourism in the normalization stage of epidemic prevention and control. (HaiShui Jin & Jinglin Xu, 2022) For example, many tourism enterprises and distributors have launched "cloud tourism" travel services online through digital technology and other media in the post-epidemic era, and some enterprises are pre-selling their services live through various social media for months after the epidemic. Travel tickets are being pre-sold through a variety of social media, and new travel media technologies are being used to promote tourism organizations' marketing by bringing tourists closer to their travel preferences, which is a direct and powerful initiative for the post-epidemic recovery of the tourism industry.

➤ *Focus On Developing The Strategy Of Rural Tourism*

The epidemic should avoid first- and second-tier cities with high population density, and tourism companies can try to shift their focus from first- and second-tier cities to third- and fourth-tier cities, and some Chinese literature mentions that in response to the epidemic should Focus on developing peripheral, short-distance, and local tourism and create new consumption hotspots in line with the rural revitalization

strategy (Guo Chaofei , 2021), rural tourism is a policy that has been vigorously introduced by the Chinese government in recent years with the aim of giving full play to the advantages of rural tourism and comprehensively promoting rural revitalization. Rural tourism products are based on the human, natural, and agricultural landscapes of local villages, and aim to provide tourism services that allow tourists to experience local folk culture. Rural tourism avoids the densely populated cities and develops special tourism products for tourists that integrate ecological tourism and agricultural landscapes.

➤ *Actively Integrate Resources To Realize The Optimal Allocation Of Enterprise Resources*

Save expenses by adopting service outsourcing and other ways, improve management efficiency by optimizing enterprise organization and management structure, and actively carry out pre-sale of new products and services to achieve the purpose of stabilizing customer source and recovering capital. Take the initiative to make good use of all applicable support policies and burden reduction policies introduced by the state and provinces and cities for tourism enterprises, including deferred tax payments, rent subsidies, and the use of financial support policies to resolve the enterprise liquidity crisis. At the same time, enterprises should adjust their budgets, compress expenses, reduce losses, control operating costs, take appropriate and rational measures, make internal adjustments, reduce expenses and divest non-performing businesses in a timely manner. Proactive subtraction, business integration, enterprise integration, etc., and strive for continuous capital chain. Human capital is the blood of an enterprise, and quality human capital is unavailable to every enterprise. During the epidemic, tourism enterprises struggled to develop, and some had to lay off employees to make up for the deficit. In fact, tourism companies can adopt a shift system to allow more vacation time for their employees. Adopting a shift system on the one hand allows companies to reduce worker expenses and helps tourism companies cut costs; on the other hand, it allows companies to retain talented people and make long-term considerations for future business after the epidemic is over.

V. CONCLUSION

The 21st century is supposed to be a time of economic globalization and rapid development of new things, but instead we have the challenge of the new pneumonia epidemic, and the world seems to have hit the pause button. The spread and outbreak of the epidemic has had a negative impact on various industries, especially tourism, a mobility-dependent industry, where the reduction in mobility has dealt a heavy blow to the tourism economy. However, the tourism industry is gradually picking up as the post-epidemic economies rebound and the demand for tourism grows. In this paper, we analyze the impact of the epidemic on the tourism industry, and draw conclusions on how to develop a new strategic plan to restore prosperity in the post-epidemic era. Through the plan, the industry rebound can not only hope on government policies or subsidies, simply through the channel reconstruction to restore the flow and quantity, but should be combined with travel and recreation, leisure and vacation, cultural and tourism exploration, intelligent tourism and other aspects to develop. And, the tourism industry as a tertiary industry, public health crisis once it occurs, making it requires a long time, industry-wide, overall measures to systematically implement the gradual recovery. Therefore, in the late stage of the epidemic, enterprises should promptly adjust their structure, accelerate the improvement of products and services, actively respond to deepen the transformation, and take advantage of good industrial integration to promote the sustainable development of the industry. In short, the epidemic prevention and control situation has undergone a fundamental change, we should take advantage of the situation and make a difference, to open a new chapter in the development of tourism.

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